

INSERVICE TEACHER TRAINING PROGRAMMES: IMPLICATIONS ON TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to assess the effect of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' effectiveness in Sotik Sub-County. In-service Teacher Training Programme is a mode of study undertaken by teachers who are already in the teaching profession. This programme is offered during the school holidays in April, August and December and in the evenings and weekends. The programme affects the teachers' performance in their respective secondary schools either positively or negatively. This study was guided by five main objectives: To determine the effect of In-service Teacher Training Programme on teacher's effectiveness on planning for instruction, on lesson content delivery, teacher's evaluation skills, on development of Student-Teacher relationship and finally to examine the effect on their use of teaching- learning resources on their teaching. The study employed descriptive survey design. 356 teachers, 36 head teachers, one Quality Assurance and Standards Officer which formed a target population of 393 respondents. To obtain the sample size a purposive sampling was used to target teachers who have undergone or undergoing In-service Teacher Training Programme. Sub-county QASO and Head teachers whose schools had ITTP teachers were interviewed. Stratified purposive sampling was used to select two teachers per school who were observed considering gender where applicable. All teachers who had undergone and those undergoing In-service Teacher Training

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Programme in the sub-county secondary schools filled the questionnaire. Data was gathered by use of a questionnaire, an interview schedule, an observation guide and documentary analysis. The data was subjected to both qualitative and quantitative analysis. The study was based on the model of Effective Schools by Lesothe (2001) who posited the seven correlates of effective schools that includes instructional leadership, high academic success, monitoring of students' progress and opportunity to learn. The data analysis was done using both descriptive (means, frequencies and tables) as well as inferential statistics (correlation). A statistically significant positive relationship between the dependent variable In-service Teacher Training Programme and effective teacher planning for instruction at a coefficient of 0.571 ($p=0.00<0.05$), positive relationship with teachers' lesson content delivery at a coefficient of 0.682 ($r=0.682$ $p<0.05$), positive relationship with teachers' student evaluation at a coefficient of 0.611 ($r=0.611$ $p<0.05$); positive relationship with teachers' development of Student - Teacher relationship at a significant coefficient of 0.622 ($r=0.622$ $p<0.05$) and a positive relationship with teachers' use of Teaching-Learning resources at a significant coefficient of 0.692 ($r=0.692$ $p<0.05$). The study recommend consented efforts of the Government, School Principals, Universities in ensuring proper rolling and management of the In-service Teacher Training Programme in order to benefit more teachers. Universities need to follow up their products (alumni) in the form of surveys, ITTP research and interaction and assess their performance in view of the training their alumni received. Further studies are recommended to establish the sources of fees for the Teachers under ITTP in the Universities and challenges thereof, which university has high number of MEd students and why as well as which gender is of high population in ITTP and to find reasons why.

Keywords: inservice teacher, teacher effectiveness, secondary schools, Kenya

1. Introduction

In-service Teacher Training Programme is teaching opportunities provided to eligible and interested teachers who cannot pursue full-time courses in the universities/college or learning institutions because they are in the teaching profession hence they attend training during the school holidays, evenings and weekends. In-service Teacher Training Programme is designed to promote and support the professional learning of teachers who are already employed and working in the classroom (Muzaffar and Rahim, 2011). According to Ginsburg (2010), the goal of school based learning professional development is to improve the knowledge skills, and commitment of

teachers so that they become more effective in planning lessons using a variety of effective approaches in their teaching and monitoring students learning as well as in undertaking other school and commitment responsibilities.

McDiarmid and Bright (2008) asserts that teachers need to know, be able to do and care about knowledge including subject matter, pedagogical content knowledge, curriculum, pedagogy, educational foundations, policy context, diverse learners and their cultures, technology, child and adolescent development, group processes and dynamics, theories of learning, motivation and assessment. He further suggests that teachers should be able to craft skills including planning, organizing and orchestrating instruction, using instructional materials and technology, disciplinary learners, managing groups, monitoring and evaluating learning, collaborating with colleagues, parents, community and social services agencies and dispositions including beliefs, attitudes, values and commitment.

Ko, Sammons and Bakkum (2013) contents that teachers are key elements in any school and effective teaching is one of the key propellers for school improvement. Subsequently, teacher effectiveness is generally referred to in terms of focus on student outcomes and the teacher behaviours and classroom processes that promote better student outcomes. They suggested that effective teachers are clear about instructional goals; knowledge about curriculum content and strategies for teaching it. They also communicate to their students what is expected of them and why; make expert use of existing instructional materials in order to devote more time to practices that enrich and clarify the content, knowledgeable about their students adapting, misconceptions in their existing, knowledge; teach students Meta-cognitive strategies and give them opportunities to master them; address higher as well a slower-level-cognitive objectives; monitor students' understanding by offering regular appropriate feedback; integrate the instruction with that in other subject areas; and accept responsibilities for student outcomes.

2. Statement of the Problem

The Government of the Republic of Kenya recognizes the importance of teacher education as one of the important levers of accelerating the attainment of Education For All (EFA) and Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). An effective teacher education program enhances a country's social-economic growth and political stability. The Government, through the Sessional paper No. 1 of 2005, a policy Framework on Education, Training and Research recommended development of a comprehensive teacher-education and service standard guidelines (MOEST, 2005). This is because

effective teaching is critical to the provision and maintenance of quality and relevant education at all levels.

Bomet County and in particular Sotik Sub-County, has not been left out. Many teachers have graduated and are enrolled in the In-service Teacher Training Programmes in various universities. According to the Bomet County Education Magazine of June 2014 the start of Mount Kenya University, Kisii University and Egerton University at Kabarnet, a good number of teachers have enrolled in the ITTP (Korir, 2014). However, despite the evident increase in number of teachers pursuing school based learning in Sotik Sub-County, the effect of this In-service Teacher Training Programme on teachers' effectiveness has not been ascertained. It is against this backdrop that this study was designed to fill the knowledge gap.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Sotik Sub-County.

4. Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this study were:

1. To establish the effect of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' student evaluation.
2. To determine the effect of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' development of Student -Teacher relationship.
3. To ascertain the effect of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' use of Teaching-Learning resources.

5. Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following questions:-

1. What are the effects of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' students' evaluation?
2. What are the effects of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' development of student-teacher relationship?
3. What are the effects of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' use of teaching-learning resources?

6. Significance of the Study

The Ministry of Education would understand the need to strengthen school-based teacher programme in country through suggesting areas of the curriculum to be strengthened and amended by the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD). The study would aid the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology to formulate policies that would dedicate In-service Teacher Training Programmes in the national catalogue for professional development of teachers.

This research would contribute significantly to the existing knowledge in the world of academics as well as bridging the gap left by other researchers on In-service Teacher Training Programme or in-service training.

The school administration would undertake a strong and visible leadership stance on pedagogical development in schools and actively support creativity, innovation and quality development of teaching and learning process.

The study would be significant to policy makers to come up with strategies and policies geared towards strengthening school-based teacher programme in Sotik Sub-County and the entire nation at large.

It would also help parents get to know the effects of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on their children's academic performance so as to bridge any gap created through employment of more teachers under their financial support popularly referred as B.O.M teachers.

Teachers would find this information useful in understanding the need to invest in quality training which would in forth lead to quality instruction to their learners; and them with knowledge and skills to enable them cope up with.

It would enable universities and other training institutions to formalize and institutionalize In-service Teacher Training Programme as a complimentary component to the continuing training courses, while establishing a solid pedagogical teachers training, where university education alternatives with classroom training.

The Students would also benefit in that teacher will be well trained on the best ways of instruction leading to better teaching services and curriculum delivery designed for the learners hence posting better academic and moral development. By learners attaining right and quality education would endeavour the country in achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the vision 2030 on education sector.

7. Theoretical framework

This study was based on the model of effective schools by Lezotte (2001). According to Lezotte, there are seven correlates of effective schools namely strong instructional leadership, clear and focused mission, safe and orderly school environment, climate of high expectations for success, frequent monitoring of student progress, positive home-school relationship and opportunity to learn and study time on task. All the correlates of effective schools, proposed by Lezotte are critical to the effective schools because they represent the leading organizational and contextual indicators that have been shown to influence student learning positively through student achievement. The seven correlates of Effective Schools are the aspects effective teachers are expected to enforce to realise better student's academic performance.

Effective school management and teaching contribute greatly to improved academic performance through clear and focused instructional leadership. Clear and focused mission articulate the overall school effectiveness. Every school stakeholder has a shared sense of purpose, understanding and core values to attainment of effective teaching and learning. Classrooms are warm and inviting and learning activities are purposeful, engaging and significant. Personalized learning environment are created by increase positive relationship amongst students and between students and teachers (Lezotte, 2001).

Frequent monitoring of students' progress enables the teachers to use the results of the assessment to adjust instructional and to cater for their varied students' capabilities. Positive home-school relations foster parents understanding, support and involvement as part of the collaborative team as parties in the education of their children leading to discipline which is the factor to good academic performance.

Opportunity to learn and student time on task guide the teacher to allocate a significant amount of time to instruction in the essential curricular areas such as the compulsory subject such as Mathematics, English, Kiswahili and Science. Students tend to learn most things purposively to time spend on it.

In summary, the Correlates of Effective Schools provide school improvement teams and student with comprehensive framework for identifying categorizing, and solving the problems the teams face in development of effective schools through effective teachers. Head teachers and teachers are pivotal in development of effective schools thus, they require training to enable them acquire new concepts and models of overcoming emerging challenges of imparting knowledge to the present generation and to meet the emerging dynamics like technological, constitutional and behavioural changes.

8. Conceptual framework

The study sought to find out the effect of In-service Teacher Training Programme on teacher's effectiveness in undertaking their professional duties in Sotik Sub-County in Bomet County. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study.

Fig.2.1: Conceptual framework showing relationship between schools based learning programme and teacher effectiveness.

Source: Researcher

Figure 1 shows how In-service Teacher Training Programmes influences teachers' effectiveness. In-service Teacher Training Programmes offer relevant courses including how to effectively plan for instructions, lesson content delivery, assessment, development of student-teacher relationships and better use and improvisation of teacher-learning resources. The teachers who have received these courses were expected to perform better in their teaching profession. The intervening variables of the study includes features such as the type of the school, teachers' teaching experiences, teachers' qualification, school management and school culture. Academic performance by the students is an indicator of effective teaching and learning. This performance can be ascertained through documentary analysis which includes principal's appraisals, awards, annual reports, QASO reports and school academic progress records.

9. Methodology

The study utilised the mixed methods approach where both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection were used and employed an ex-post facto and descriptive survey research designs. The target population was all teachers and head teachers in all the 36 secondary schools in Sotik Sub-County who have undergone the In-service Teacher Training Programme and the Quality Assurance and Standards Officer of the Sub-County. The study targeted all the 36 Principals of the 36 secondary schools, one Sub-County Quality Assurance and Standards Officer, 182 teachers who have undergone or undergoing school based learning, totalling to 289 respondents.

Validity and reliability of instruments were ascertained. After the test-retest, the instruments attained a reliability coefficient of 0.70 using the Cronbach alpha coefficient which was considered high enough to continue with data collection.

9.1 Teaching Experience after Enrolling for School Based Learning

The research finally established the teacher's years of experience after enrolling in In-service Teacher Training Programme. The findings are as shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2: Teaching Experience

The findings in figure 2 above revealed that the majority (28%) of the purposively sampled teachers joined ITTP over 6 years ago meaning they already graduated. This was followed by 26% between 5-6 years either graduated or about to. Only 22% of the sampled teachers were enrolled 3-4 years and another 12% were enrolled 1-2 years ago. This would be interpreted to infer that majority of the teachers have already gone through the programme hence the number is reducing. It can also infer that new teachers can no longer afford to enrol to the programme or have preferred other available study programmes for example, regular programme of studying through study leave or distance learning mode of study. It was necessary to examine the length of experience of the teachers after enrolling through ITTP since this will influence the value of information they would give with regards to effects of In-service Teacher Training Programmes on teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools. The length of experience was found to be adequate enough for this study.

9.2 Effects of ITTP on Teachers' student evaluation

The researcher also sought to establish the effects of In-service Teacher Training Programme on teachers' student evaluation. The findings are as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Effects of ITTP on Teachers' Student Evaluation

Statement	SA(1)	A(2)	N(3)	D(4)	SD(5)
After undergoing In-service Teacher Training Programme, I usually ask individual students questions as they as well ask questions on the lesson content.	47%	16%	1%	26%	10%
In-service Teacher Training Programme has enabled me to:-	35%	55%	1 %	8%	1%
(a) Initiate discussions in class through responding to students questions					
(b) Acknowledge student's attempts	33%	33%	11%	10%	13%
(c) Reinforce correct students' answers	39%	39%	6%	10%	6%
(d) Aid in correcting students' wrong attempts.	40%	39%	1 %	13%	7%
In-service Teacher Training Programme has bettered my understanding of the varied students' abilities and developed the urge to support weak students through class involvement, group work, and individualized remedial.	35%	37%	5%	13%	10%
Before undergoing In-service Teacher Training Programme, I used to conclude my lessons by asking lesson summary questions and giving assignments.	25%	33%	13%	10%	19%
After undergoing In-service Teacher Training Programme, I usually conclude my lessons by asking lesson summary questions, revision questions and giving assignments.	35 %	44%	5%	4%	12%

Table 1 indicates that 63% agreed that after undergoing In-service Teacher Training Programme, they usually ask individual students questions as they as well ask questions on the lesson content. It is also indicated that In-service Teacher Training Programme has enabled 90% of the teachers to initiate discussions in class through responding to student's questions, 66% of the teachers to acknowledge student's attempts, 78% to reinforce correct students' answers and 79% to aid in correcting students' wrong attempts.

Another majority (72%) of the respondents agreed that In-service Teacher Training Programme has bettered their understanding of the varied students' abilities and developed the urge to support weak students through class involvement, group work, and individualized remedial. Furthermore, teacher's ability to conclude lessons by asking lesson summary questions and giving assignments increased from 58%

majority to 79% majority after attending In-service Teacher Training Programmes. A majority (65%) of the respondents agreed that In-service Teacher Training Programmes has enabled them to mark and make corrections on students' assignments before every lesson.

Finally a majority (90%) of the respondents agreed that In-service Teacher Training Programmes has trained them to provide students with further reading areas to enhance their understanding and prepare for the next lesson after every lesson.

This findings agree with Fairtest (2007), that assessment of student learning is undergoing profound changes and at the same time, reforms are taking place in learning goals and content standards, curriculum, instruction, the education of teachers, and the relationships among parents, communities, schools, government, and business. These principles provide a vision of how to transform assessment systems and practices as part of wider school reform, with a particular focus on improving classrooms assessment, while ensuring large-scale assessment which also supports learning. To best serve learning, assessment must be integrated with curriculum and induction.

High quality assessment must rest on strong educational foundation. These foundations include organizing schools to meet the learning needs of all their students, understanding students learning, and providing equitable and adequate opportunity to learn as stressed by Fairtest, (2007). He further agrees that the principles reflect an "ideal" assessment and the education systems must move towards meeting these principles if assessment is to play a positive role in improving education for all students. The primary purpose of assessment is to improve standard's learning, and subsequently assessment systems, including classroom organization with the primary purpose of improving student learning.

Finally McBer (2000) concurred that effective teachers employ a range of assessment methods and techniques to monitor learners understanding of lessons and work.

These could be tests, competitions, questioning or regular marking of written work. He further asserts that effective teachers look for gains in learning, gaps in knowledge and areas of understanding through their day-to-day work with learners, and they work with by encouraging them to judge the success of their own work and instruct them to set for themselves targets. Educators assess student learning through such methods as structured and informal observations and interviews projects and tasks, tests, performance and exhibitions, audio and videotapes experiences, portfolios, and journals. Multiple-choice methods and assessment intended to rank order or compare students, if used, are a limited part of the assessment system hence the need for teacher training on students' evaluation and assessment.

10. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study as summarized above, it can be concluded that In-service Teacher Training Programmes has a positive relationship with teachers' student evaluation at a coefficient of 0.611($r=0.611$ $p<0.05$); teachers' development of Student-Teacher relationship at a significant coefficient of 0.622($r=0.622$ $p<0.05$) teachers' use of Teaching-Learning resources at a significant coefficient of 0.692($r=0.692$ $p<0.05$).The study was successful in addressing its objectives. Given the foregoing, the study arrived at the following conclusions:

1. Increased training through In-service Teacher Training Programme predicted improvement on teachers' student evaluation.
2. Increased training through In-service Teacher Training Programme predicted improvement on teachers' development of Student -Teacher relationship.
3. Increased training through In-service Teacher Training Programme predicted improvement on teachers' use of Teaching-Learning resources.

The study hence conclude that school based programmes through the Universities contribute to the transformation of society through research and the generation of new knowledge and skills by training competent and effective teachers. So far, results from this study indicate that teachers were academically well prepared by universities.

11. Recommendations

The following factors provides recommendations emanating from the analysis results and findings of the study,

1. It is recommended that the capacity of institutions of higher learning should be increased to allow for effective training of more teachers in need of acquiring more knowledge and skills
2. It is also recommended that school principals should enhance more training of teachers by developing an incentive mechanism for principals, teachers, facilitators and mentors. This will make teachers professionally competent, that is improving classroom activities of teachers, increasing teachers knowledge and improving the quality of teaching. Induction program for newly deployed teachers is recommended to be implemented.
3. Policy makers can promote wider debate on such fundamental concepts across the sector. Active debate invites exchange among stakeholders, critical analysis of evidence and ideas, and innovation. It moves beyond simple dissemination of

tools or sharing of best practices, and places a stronger focus on transformation of teaching and cultures of learning. This process is essential if ideas are to gain any real traction in the sector.

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